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Review Article

**A REVIEW BASED ON DRUG REPURPOSING: AN VIRTUAL
TOOL IN MODERN DRUG DISCOVERY**

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Abstract:

Drug repurposing involves using existing medications for new therapeutic purposes, gaining significant attention during the covid -19 pandemic as a means to expedite drug discovery and address urgent healthcare demands. The process starts with identifying potential drug candidates, followed by evaluating their effectiveness through preclinical models and advancing to phase2 clinical trials. identification can be achieved through both computational and experimental methods, leveraging public drug databases and various data sources, including primary research, clinical trials, and anecdotal evidence of off- label uses. Researchers utilize artificial intelligence and bioinformatics tools to explore drug –protein interactions, often integrating genetic information, clinical data, molecular docking, and other analyses to optimize outcomes. This article outlines the strategies for drug repurposing and list various drugs that have been successfully repurposed along with their new indications.

Key words: drug repurposing, clinical trials, molecular docking, drug discovery, post- market safety

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INTRODUCTION:

Drug repurposing involves using an already existing medication for a new treatment or medical condition that it was not originally designed to address. This approach often arises unexpectedly and can reveal that the side effects of a drug may indicate its potential effectiveness for different conditions.

Typically, these drugs have already undergone safety evaluations in humans and have been developed for efficacy in a specific disease, making it possible to move directly to preclinical and clinical trials. This strategy helps to bypass the lengthy drug development process, ultimately lowering both risks and costs. [1-4]

❖ **Stages of drug repurposing [5]**❖ **Significance of drug repurposing**

To bring a new drug to market, companies must navigate strict regulations, which can be costly and time-consuming due to the complex physical and chemical properties of drugs and the challenges in scaling up production. This situation encourages pharmaceuticals companies and research institutions to consider repurposing already approved drugs for new uses, particularly for disease where existing treatments are lacking.

Investigation of molecules that have not proven effective for their original intended use can lead to their revival through repurposing. This is particularly valuable for rare diseases that are difficult to diagnose and treat due to limited resources. For example: certain autoimmune disorders and rare cancers often lack clear hereditary causes, complicating their treatment

Repurposing drugs is generally more cost effective and quicker than traditional drug development allowing effective treatments to reach sooner and helping to manage rising development costs, which can reduce the financial burden on patients

In contrast to new investigational drugs, which often face high failure rates due to unknown safety and efficacy. Repurposed drugs come with existing safety and efficacy data. This information allows researchers to make better-informed decisions throughout the development process, cutting both time and costs significantly.

A notable success story in drug repurposing is sildenafil, initially developed for hypertension, which found a new application in treating erectile dysfunction and was later approved for pulmonary hypertension as well. With advancements in technology and computational tools, starting drug discovery with an already – approved medication has become a more accessible strategy. Recent data shows that about 30% of new drugs approved by the FDA in recent years have been repurposed.

While drug repurposing presents significant opportunities for out-licensing due to the established characteristics of these drugs. It is also crucial to ensure that targeting a new condition doesn't undermine the drug's market potential for its original use. Rare disease, in particular, represent a critical area for repurposing efforts, as they often lack

standard treatment options and face urgent medical needs. [6]

❖ **Difference between traditional drug discovery system and drug repurposing**

➤ **Traditional drug discovery**

- Discovery and preclinical
- Safety review
- Clinical research
- More time consuming
- High investment

➤ **Drug repurposing**

- It includes 4 stages
- Compound identification
- Compound acquisition
- Development
- Less time consuming
- Less investment

❖ **An ideal candidate for repurposing**

A drug that has completed clinical development and been approved for market use can be a strong candidate for repurposing especially if it has established safety and toxicity data. In such cases, the drug may bypass further clinical trials if sufficient supporting data is available. Ideal repurposing candidates include drugs that have failed in development for reasons unrelated to safety. [7] A notable example is Viagra which was initially

developed for hypertension and angina but found its use in treating erectile dysfunction during clinical trials. Some drugs that were previously abandoned due to safety concerns have later been repurposed for different indications. Thalidomide, originally used to treat nausea in pregnant women, caused severe birth defects and was subsequently banned in many countries. It was later repurposed for treating leprosy and multiple myeloma, although this has sparked debate within the scientific community. When considering repurposing it is crucial to weigh the benefit to risk ratio, and regulatory authorities must carefully evaluate whether the potential advantages justify the risks compared to existing therapies.

❖ **For drug Strategies repurposing**

This method typically relies on public drug databases, incorporating data from primary and translational research, clinical trials, [8] anecdotal reports of off-label uses, and other published human data. Researchers employ artificial intelligence algorithms and bioinformatics tools to systematically explore interactions between drugs and protein targets. In silico drug repositioning is a valuable technology that offers notable benefits, such as increased speed and reduced costs. There are generally three approaches used: computational, biological experimental, and mixed approach

DISEASE-ORIENTED	DRUG-ORIENTED INFORMATION OF DRUGS	TREATMENT ORIENTED
Information on disease	Off-label drugs	Disease omics data
Disease omics data	Phenotypic screening	All drug information related to treatment strategies
Genetics data of disease	Target 3D structure drugs	Genetics genomics

❖ **Challenges**

Drug repurposing has been gaining interest, but its application is limited due to various challenges. One major issue is the lack of clear regulatory guidelines for repurposing drug candidates, making it difficult for new startups to provide necessary information to regulatory agencies. [9] Additionally, while patents and the orphan drug act can offer some exclusivity for new uses of repurposed drugs, this doesn't prevent doctors from prescribing them off-label.

Some drugs, like thalidomide and rapamycin, have received extra exclusivity through sudden regulatory changes that allow patients to access affordable therapies. However, the absence of a defined exclusivity path remains a significant obstacle to utilizing repurposed drugs.

More ever repurposing candidates can pose times risks, especially if they have previously failed for

their original intended use. To mitigate this it's advisable to develop a branched program where a lead compound is tested for multiple indications at once. This strategy can help reduce time risks and the chance of losing intellectual property, which would otherwise require a significant investment to reprofile the same molecule. Overall, effective drug repurposing demands a deep understanding of biological and molecular pathways.

Understanding how a drug interacts with endogenous bio molecules is crucial for successful repurposing. By having comprehensive knowledge of the drug and its affected pathways, the risks associated with repurposing can be significantly reduced. [10]

Pharmaceutical companies often prioritize cost-effective and profitable research areas. However, when it comes to repurposing drugs for rare or neglected disease, there's no guarantee of substantial

economic returns. This makes it more appealing for companies to focus on more established and specialized research directions. Additionally, the lack of financial incentives and research funding presents a major challenge. For instance, there are few motivations for companies to invest in drugs for rare conditions, like pediatric cancers, where the return on investment is uncertain. This hesitation can stall the traditional drug discovery process.

There are also other hurdles to navigate when conducting clinical trials with repurposed drugs. Proof-of-concept and preclinical studies might not always demonstrate scientifically validated efficacy, and initiating phase I clinical trials can require a significant financial investment. Moreover, recruiting enough patients for large clinical trials can be difficult for rare diseases due to limited patient populations. Ensuring product safety in elderly patients and those with comorbidities is also essential.

If the intellectual property rights for a drug have expired, finding a new indication may result in minimal returns and could lead to legal complications for the developer. There is often only a brief period to recover development costs before generic alternatives enter market. Given all these challenges, successful drug repurposing necessitates innovative strategies.

❖ **Brief statement for repurposing approaches [12]**

1. Phenotypic in vitro assays

- **Challenges:**
Navigating hit validation and target identification can be quite complex. Some promising compounds may falter due to poor pharmacokinetics, which might prevent them from performing well in initial screens.
- **Significance:**
Despite these challenges, multiple independent screens can reveal effective candidates, accelerating their advancement into clinical trials. This method effectively highlights compounds that can have real-world impacts.
- **Examples:**
Pimozide and tamoxifen, originally used to treat psychiatric disorders and breast cancer, respectively, have shown unexpected potential in targeting toxoplasma through novel pathways

2. Target-based method

- **Challenges:**

This approach often struggles with low productivity, and many candidates may not perform as well as hoped. However, even low-affinity hits can be refined for better efficacy.

- **Significance:**
The method allows for confirmation of target engagement, providing insights into biological impacts at the cellular level, which can lead to the optimization of drug profiles.
- **Examples:**
L-type calcium blockers, initially intended for heart conditions, are being explored as potential treatments for cryptococcosis, demonstrating the versatility of this approach.

3. Pathways or network-based methods

- **Challenges:**
Integrating cellular contexts and genetic nuances into predictions can be challenging. But it's essential for enhancing accuracy in drug discovery.
- **Significance:**
This approach opens the door to unexpected and novel investigational probes, potentially revolutionizing drug development by identifying new therapeutic targets.
- **Examples:**
GV1001 is being reconsidered for its potential to treat testosterone-induced benign prostatic hyperplasia illustrating the surprising applications of this method.

4. Signature-based approaches

- **Challenges:**
While these methods provide valuable initial data, they often require deeper analysis to uncover more comprehensive insights.
- **Significance:**
Signature-based approaches can reveal hidden mechanisms of action, paving the way for innovative drug candidates and fresh therapeutic possibilities.
- **Examples:**
The exploration of unique drug signatures aim to identify new treatments for a typical conditions show casing the transformative potential for this approach.

Repurposing access:

Drug repurposing can happen in two fascinating ways: through serendipitous discovery or via structured, hypothesis-driven strategies. The latter often employs a blend of experimental and

computational techniques, shedding light on the intricate mechanisms and pathways at play in various diseases.

In the experimental realm, technique like binding assays and phenotypic screening are used to uncover how compounds interact with biological components and to sift through large libraries for promising candidates. On the computational side, strategies are diverse- ranging from target-based to pathway-based

approaches-each offering a unique lens on the drug discovery process. These methods not only save costs but also amplify the effectiveness of drug development by integrating insights from cheminformatics, bioinformatics, and systems biology. By tapping into existing data about targets, drugs, and disease pathways, researchers can craft innovative strategies and optimize the planning of clinical trials, paving the way for novel therapeutic breakthroughs and it summarized in below chart

Binding assays:

Techniques like proteomics and mass spectrometry allow for the identification of targets for different compounds. One example is the cellular thermal stability assay, which assesses how compounds with high cellular affinity stabilize target proteins through temperature changes. Recently, cellular targets for the tyrosine kinase inhibitor crizotinib were identified, and quinone reductase2 was found to be an off-target for acetaminophen at the cellular level.

Phenotypic screening:

The phenotypic screening method has been employed identify molecules and biologics that have received regulatory approval. These methods typically do not involve pharmaceutical or biological data, making them less effective in clarifying the mechanisms of actions of drugs. They largely rely on chance discoveries from tests focused on specific diseases and medications. [13] The benefits of methods like off-label use and phenotypic screening are that they offer a greater likelihood of being applicable to a wide range of drugs or conditions.

Target based methods:

This method relies on specific knowledge about targets, including 3D protein structures. knowledge-based approaches require information on drugs or diseases, such as adverse effects, regulatory approvals, clinical trial records, and published disease bio markers or pathways. these methods allow researchers to efficiently screen numerous drug molecules with known chemical structures

Target -based drug repositioning methods include:

In -vitro and in vivo high-throughput and or high-content screening for specific proteins or bio markers. In- silico screening of drugs or compounds from libraries such as ligand -based screening or docking Target -based methods enhance drug discovery chances because they are directly connected to disease mechanisms, and integrating target information with drug repurposing increases the likelihood of identifying therapeutically valuable compounds. [14]

Knowledge – based methods:

These methods utilize bioinformatics and cheminformatics to integrate various types of information, such as drug and drug-target networks, chemical structures, clinical trial data, FDA approval labels, and signaling or metabolic pathways, into drug repositioning studies. The data available from blinded and target-based methods may not adequately uncover new mechanisms beyond existing targets. In contrast, knowledge-based methods leverage known information to predict unknown mechanisms, including novel drug targets, unexpected drug-drug similarities, and new disease biomarkers. Enhance the accuracy of predictions in the drug repositioning process.

Signature-based methods:

Signature-based drug repurposing methods utilize gene signatures derived from disease omics data, with or without treatment, to identify unknown off- target or disease mechanisms. This genomic data can be accessed through public databases like NCBI-GEO, SRA sequence read archive, CAMP connectively map, and CCLE cancer cell line encyclopedia. These methods aid in revealing previously unknown mechanisms of action for drugs and molecules. Computational approaches often focus on molecular - level mechanisms, including significantly altered genes.

Pathway or network -based methods:

This approach leverages genetic disease information, available signaling or metabolic pathways, and protein interaction networks to create disease - specific pathways, helping identify key targets for drug repurposing. It streamlines broad signaling networks, focusing on a few critical purposes. By employing pathway analysis and network biology techniques, this method uncovers vital pathways from various data types- genetic, genomic, proteomic, and metabolic – to discover new targets for repositioned drugs. For example, analyzing the signaling mechanisms in different metastatic subtypes of breast cancer can be challenging due to the complexity of existing pathways and gene signatures.

Targeted mechanism – based methods:

These methods combine treatment- related genetic data, existing signaling pathway information, and protein interaction networks to uncover the mechanisms behind how drugs work. The goal is to

identify the pathways that drugs target or affect -both on – target and off – target – by analyzing drugs omics data collected before and after treatment. Drug resistance is a significant challenge in cancer therapy, as patients may initially respond well to a medication but often develop resistance after a few months. Therefore, understanding the mechanism of drug action is crucial for identifying more effective drug targets however, there is a lack of studies focused on mechanism – based approaches that use sophisticated computational models to predict drug effect and associated pathways, largely due to challenges involved in creating effective models.

Molecular docking:

Molecular docking is a flexible technique used to predict how a protein interacts with a small molecule ligand and to determine their spatial arrangement.it can involve docking a known drug across various target structure or screening a database of approved drugs against a specific target. This method is efficient for rapidly assessing large libraries of ligands and targets, offering extensive sampling options [15]. To perform docking, the 3D structures of the targets are needed, typically obtained through methods like crystallography, nuclear magnetic resonance or comparative modeling. some limitations include the reliance on approximate scoring functions and less than perfect algorithms for binding mode placement. However, these issues can be addressed by refining docking results using more precise scoring methods.

Application of drug repurposing in drug discovery

In addition to developing new therapies like immunotherapy and host-directed treatments, scientists globally are also focused on repurposing existing drugs for SARS- COV-2. One notable example is metformin, an antidiabetic medication that exhibits anticancer properties by reducing the risk of various cancers, inhibiting cancer cell growth and migration, promoting apoptosis, and decreasing epithelial- mesenchymal transition and metastasis. Drug repurposing also addresses antibiotic resistance issues, such as the emergence of drug- resistant tuberculosis strains worldwide. Pyridomycin, an antibiotic discovered in the 1950s, has been repurposed to treat TB as a substitute for isoniazid. [16] For further details, see in the below table, which lists repurposed drugs along with their original and new uses.

1. Cancer diseases

Drug	discovered	repurposed	Mechanism of action
Anastrozole	Ovulation induction	Breast cancer	Aromatase inhibitor
Capecitabine	Anti Colon cancer	Breast cancer	Prodrug converted to 5-fluorouracil, inhibits DNA synthesis
Carboplatin	Anti tumor	Active against fungal biofilms	DNA cross-linker, inhibiting DNA replication
cisplatin	antitumor	Active against fungal biofilms	DNA cross -linker, inhibits DNA replication
Docetaxel	Hormone-refractory prostate cancer	Breast cancer and active against fungal biofilms	Inhibits microtubule depolymerization, disrupting mitosis
Doxorubicin	antibiotic	Various cancer	Intercalates DNA, inhibits topoisomerase2
Edaravone	Neuroprotective for stroke and ALS	Multiple sclerosis	Free radical scavenger
Everolimus	Immuno suppresent during organ transplants	Breast cancer	mTOR inhibitor, inhibits cell proliferation
Fulverstrant	antiestrogen	Breast cancer	Selective estrogen receptor down regulator
Gemcitabine	Anti-viral drugs	Breast cancer	Inhibits DNA synthesis
Goserelin	Prostate cancer, uterine fibroids	Breast cancer	GnRH agonist, suppress testosterone production
Methotrexate	leukemia	Breast cancer	Inhibits dihydrofolate reductase, affecting DNA synthesis
nelfinavir	HIV protease inhibitor	Solid tumor	Inhibits viral protease, disrupting viral replication
Raloxifene	osteoporosis	Breast cancer	Selective estrogen receptor modulator
Tamoxifen	Breast cancer, ovulation induction	Antibacterial and antifungal	Selective estrogen receptor modulator
Thalidomide	antiemetic	Hansen's disease, leprosy	Angiogenesis inhibitors, immune modulation
vinblastine	Hodgkin lymphoma, non-Hodgkin's lymphoma	Breast cancer	Inhibits microtubule formation

2. Infectious disease

Drug	discovered	Repurposed	Mechanism of action
Avermectin B1a	Anti- infective	Active against fungal biofilms	Increase chloride permeability, paralyzing parasites
Artesunate	Anti- infective	Active against fungal biofilms	Generate free radicals, damaging parasite proteins
Bacitracin	Anti - infective	Active against fungal biofilms	Disrupts bacterial cell wall synthesis
clarithromycin	Anti -infective	Active against fungal biofilms	Inhibits bacterial protein synthesis
iodoquinol	Anti -infective	Active against fungal biofilms	Anti protozoal activity, exact mechanism unclear
ivermectin	Anti - parasitic	Effective against SARS-COV-2	Increases chloride permeability in nematodes
nitazoxanide	Antiprotozoal agent	Influenza	Inhibits parasite energy metabolism
Pyrvinium pamoate	Anti -infective	Active against fungal biofilms	Inhibits helminth energy metabolism
Quinacrine	Helminthiasis	Antibacterial and antifungal	Inhibits RNA and protein synthesis
Rifampicin	Anti-infective	Active against fungal biofilms	Inhibits bacterial RNA polymerase

3. Neurological disorders

DRUG	DISCOVERED	REPURPOSED	MECHANISM OF ACTION
Edaravone	Neuroprotective agent in stroke and ALS	Multiple sclerosis	Free radical scavenger
Dexpramipexole	ALS and other neurological disease	Hypereosinophilic syndrome	Glutamate antagonist
fluoxetine	antidepressant	Active against fungal biofilms	Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor
Riluzol	Glutamate antagonist	Secondary progressive multiple sclerosis	Inhibits glutamate release and transmission

4. Autoimmune diseases

Drug	discovered	repurposed	Mechanism of action
azathioprine	Crohn's disease	Antibacterial and antifungal	Immunosuppressant, inhibits purine synthesis
Cyclosporine	Anti- inflammatory	Active against fungal biofilms	Inhibits T- cell activation and cytokine production
Disulfiram	Reduces ethanol tolerance in alcoholism	Metastatic breast cancer and Alzheimer's disease	Inhibits aldehyde dehydrogenase, alters neurotransmitter levels
Human albumin	Blood additive	Immune-restoration	Modulates immune response

methotrexate	leukemia	Breast cancer	Inhibits dihydrofolate reductase, affects DNA synthesis
Mycophenolic acid	immunosuppressant	Anticancer	Inhibits lymphocyte proliferation
Tacrolimus	Anti-inflammatory	Active against fungal biofilms	Inhibits T-cell activation
Tocilizumab	Immunosuppressive for cytokine release syndrome	Severe COVID -19 infection	IL-6 receptor antagonist

5. Cardiovascular disease

Drug	Discovered	Repurposed	Mechanism of action
Digoxin	Treatment for cardiac diseases	Anticancer	Inhibits Na ⁺ /K ⁺ ATPase, increasing intracellular calcium
Losartan	Blood pressure reduction	Alzheimer disease	Angiotensin 2 receptor blocker
Propranolol	antiarrhythmic	Active against fungal biofilms	Non- selective beta-adrenergic antagonist
Atorvastatin	Hypercholesterolemia	Cavernous angioma	HMG -CoA reductase inhibitor
Fenofibrate	Reduces triglyceride -rich particles	Reduces macrophage recruitment in abdominal aortic aneurysm	PPAR-alpha agonist
Verapamil	Anti arrhythmic	Active against fungal biofilms	Calcium channel blocker

6. Metabolic disorders

Drug	Discovered	Repurposed	Mechanism of action
Metformin	Diabetes	Anti-nonsmall cell lung cancer	Activates Amp- activated protein kinase
Fenofibrate	Reduces triglyceride- rich particles	Reduces macrophage recruitment	Activates PPAR-alpha
Finasteride	Benign prostatic hyperplasia	Antibacterial and antifungal	5- alpha- reductase inhibitors

7. Fertility disorders

Drug	Discovered	Repurposed	Mechanism of action
Anastrozole	Ovulation induction	Breast cancer	Aromatase inhibitor
Clomiphene	Fertility	Antibacterial and antifungal	Estrogen receptor modulator
Letrozole	Ovulation induction	Breast cancer	Aromatase inhibitor

8. Respiratory diseases

Drug	Discovered	Repurposed	Mechanism of action
Favipiravir	Inhibits of RNA-dependent RNA polymerase of virus	Effective against SARS-CoV-2	Inhibits viral RNA polymerase
Remdesvir	Inhibitors of RNA – dependent RNA polymerase in virus	Effective against SARS-CoV-2	Inhibits viral RNA polymerase
Ribavirin	Anti-viral drug	Effective against SARS-CoV-2	Inhibits viral replication, nucleoside analog
Tocilizumab	Immunosuppressive drug	Severe COVID -19 infection	IL- 6 receptor antagonist

9. Fungal infections

Drug	Discovered	Repurposed	Mechanism of action
Ketorolac	Anti-inflammatory	Active against fungal biofilms	Non- selective NSAID
Meloxicam	Anti – inflammatory	Active against fungal biofilms	COX-2 selective NSAID
Amiloride	Acid-sensing ion channel antagonist	Active against fungal bio films	ENac inhibitor
Aripiprazole	Antidepressant	Active against fungal biofilms	Partial dopamine agonist
Artesunate	Anti - infective	Active against fungal biofilms	Inhibits parasite detoxification enzymes
Avermectin B1a	Anti-infective	Active against fungal biofilms	Enhances GABA neurotransmission
Benzbromarone	Vasodilator	Active against fungal bio films	Inhibits urate reabsorption
Bleomycin	Antitumor	Active against fungal bio films	Inhibits urate reabsorption
clarithromycin	Anti-infective	Active against fungal biofilms	Macrolide antibiotic
Dihydroartemisinin	Anti-infective	Active against fungal biofilms	Generates free radicals
Imipramine	Antipsychotic	Active against fungal biofilms	Tricyclic antidepressant, inhibits reuptake of nor epinephrine and serotonin
Iodoquinol	Anti- infective	Active against fungal biofilms	May interfere with nucleic acid synthesis

Recent case studies of repurposed drug:

Since many of the molecules selected for repurposing are already approved, the likelihood of failure when discovering new uses is significantly lower. This not only decreases the risk associated with drug development but also streamlines the process.

Repurposing existing drugs present a valuable opportunity for developing therapies for rare diseases, as evidenced by numerous studies exploring new uses for already- approved medications for instance, amyloid- beta is a key player in the progression of alzheimer's disease. Recently, astrazeneca's previously abandoned cancer drug, saracatinib -a dual kinase inhibitor – was discovered to affect amyloid -beta signaling in the brain, leading to a rescue of synapse loss in mouse models. Currently, a phase 2 clinical trials is assessing saracatinib's effectiveness in alzheimer's patients.

Another interesting case involves acetazolamide, commonly prescribed for altitude sickness, which has shown promise when combined with temozolomide for treating glioblastoma. This combination therapy has led to longer survival in mice with glioblastoma, particularly in those with tumors exhibiting BCL-3 over expression

In a recent study, Crvz-Muniz et al explored the antimicrobial potential of mitomycin -c traditionally an anticancer agent. They found that MMC could be repurposed to combat persistent bacterial infections caused by *Acinetobacter baumannii*, thanks to its broad cytotoxic effects. Similarly Gertis et al. investigated toremifene, another anticancer drug, and discovered it could inhibit the growth of oral bacteria like *porphyromonas gingivalis* and *streptococcus mutans*. Their finding suggested that toremifene disrupts membranes rather than targeting DNA, RNA, protein synthesis pathways.

Additionally, costabile et al. highlighted niclosamide, an anthelmintic drug, for its anti-virulence properties against *pseudomonas aeruginosa* lung infections .they results in terms of cytotoxicity ,providing a compelling case for further exploration of niclosamide as a treatment for lung infections caused by *p.aeruginosa*.

CONCLUSIONS:

Many diseases still lack effective therapeutic options, and drug repurposing allows for the exploration of the untapped potential of various molecules. To enhance drug repurposing efforts, a deeper understanding and a more integrated approach combining computational and experimental methods

are essential to improve the success rates of repurposed drugs.

Drug repurposing presents valuable opportunities for both the pharmaceutical industry and academic researchers in the realm of drug development. It holds great promise for discovering new applications for previously established medications, however, there are challenges implementing drug repurposing today. Fortunately, these hurdles can be addressed with the help of advanced technologies.

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